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Good practice guide

Use of the prototype sources for the near-infrared spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the near-infrared spectral range.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Infrared (IR) radiation: Optical radiation for which the wavelengths are longer than those for visible radiation. For infrared radiation, the range between 780 nm and 1 mm is commonly subdivided into:

IR-A: 780 nm to 1400 nm;

IR-B: 1.4 μm to 3.0 μm ;

IR-C: 3 μm to 1 mm

(see 17-21-004 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

According to ISO 20473:2007, near-infrared (NIR) radiation includes the IR-A and IR-B spectral range, i.e., 780 nm to 3000 nm. The IR-C spectral range is divided into mid-infrared (MIR; 3 μm to 50 μm) and far-infrared (FIR; 50 μm to 1 mm).

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$, where Φ_e is the radiant flux and A is the area on which the radiant flux is incident. The irradiance is expressed in W m^{-2} (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realisation of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realisation of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$, with respect to wavelength, λ : $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $\text{W m}^{-2} \text{nm}^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

3. Source based on red LEDs and IR phosphors

3.1. Design description

The source is based on a LED board by Intelligent LED Solutions (ILC-ONA7-RDOR-SC201-WIR200), which consists of seven OSRAM OSOLON™ SSL 80 LEDs (GA CS8PM1.23), electrically connected in series. Each LED chip is packaged with a silicone lens to reduce the half-value angle to typically less 40°.

The LED board is integrated in an aluminium housing, which hosts phosphors developed and deployed by PhosphorTech Corporation. Two different phosphors, both emitting mainly in the IR-A spectral range, are combined in the housing, but are spatially separated. Three LEDs are used to excite the shorter-wavelength phosphors and four LEDs for the longer-wavelength phosphors. The spatial arrangement is chosen to be symmetric around the centre of the housing for each type of phosphor.

To achieve stable and repeatable operating conditions, the aluminium housing is placed on a thermoelectric cooler (Arroyo Instruments 286-01 TECMount) which cools both, the LED board and the aluminium housing containing the phosphors. A graphite sheet is used between the TEC's thermal plate and the source to ensure high thermal conductivity.

The different components of the source are shown in Figure 1 and a photo of the source in operation is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Drawing of the source based on seven LEDs and two different phosphors (short- and long-wavelength) emitting in the IR-A spectral range.

Figure 2: Picture of the source.

3.2. Specifications

The dimensional drawings of the source mounted on the thermoelectric cooler (TEC) are shown in Figure 3. The phosphors are held inside cylindrical holes of 5 mm diameter inside the aluminium housing and are excited by the LEDs behind them.

Figure 3: Drawing of the source mounted on the cold plate of the TEC (lengths in mm).

Figure 4: Linear plot of the spectral irradiance of the source at a distance of 300 mm.

Figure 5: Logarithmic plot of the source's spectral irradiance at a distance of 300 mm compared to spectral irradiance of a FEL 1000 lamp measured at a distance of 700 mm.

The measured spectral irradiance of the source, measured at a distance of 300 mm, is shown in Figure 4. In Figure 5, the same source's spectrum at 300 mm is shown on a logarithmic scale together with the spectrum of a FEL 1000 lamp, measured at a distance of 700 mm. Clearly, the two different spectral irradiances (at different measurement distances) differ between 2 and 3 orders of magnitude, see 3.5 Limitations for more details.

The residual transmitted light of the LED with a peak wavelength of 625 nm is dominant. At 710 nm, the spectral irradiance from the short-wavelength phosphor peaks at $2.3 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and continuously decreases into the infrared spectral range, until it reaches $0.2 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ at 1150 nm. The emission of the long-wavelength phosphor mainly covers the spectral interval between 1200 nm and 1350 nm (above $0.4 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$) with an additional minor peak at 1450 nm (max. $0.1 \text{ mW m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$).

3.3. Safety and handling instructions

The source has been assessed according to the standard for photobiological safety of lamps and lamp systems, EN IEC 62471:2006. The source is found to belong to the Exempt group of lamps, see results in Annex A Photobiological safety.

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- The source should only be moved or adjusted when switched off.
- Current to the LEDs must not be applied when the TEC is inactive.
- An external, current-limited power supply must be used. The applied forward LED current must not exceed 1000 mA.
- No reverse bias should be applied to the LEDs.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames.

3.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermoelectric cooling

For reproducibility, the TEC should be always operated at the same temperature (25 °C recommended) and large gradients between the TEC and the ambient temperature should be avoided. The linear temperature dependence of the LED's centroid wavelength is approximately $0.14 \text{ nm } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and the LED's radiant flux changes by approximately $-0.4 \% \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ around the TEC temperature of 25 °C for a fix LED forward current of 700 mA.

Electrical parameters

The seven LEDs must be operated with an external constant current source and should be switched on only when the TEC is active. The forward current range is 150 mA to 1000 mA, however, the source is designed to be operated at 700 mA. At the recommended forward current, the forward voltage drop is expected to be less than 18 V.

Alignment and reference plane

For alignment purposes, the source has a dust protection cap with a cross-hair at its centre. It can be used to align the input optics of the detector by means of a laser. A mirror can be placed on the cap to observe the reflected laser beam. The reference plane for the distance setting is the outer plane of the source's aluminium housing, see Figure 3. Due to the limited output of the source, a measurement distance of 300 mm from the reference plane is recommended.

Spatial homogeneity

Due to the short measurement distance and the relatively large effective area of the source, the spatial homogeneity at the measurement plane is not ideal, see 3.5 Limitations. Hence, a correction factor needs to be determined and applied for different input optics diameters.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of 48 h should be allowed (see 3.5 Limitations).

Before the first use, the source should be seasoned for at least 1000 h and the output monitored in regular intervals.

3.5. Limitations

Non-ideal spatial homogeneity

A measurement of the relative spatial irradiance distribution is shown in Figure 6. As can be seen from the figure, the non-ideal homogeneity at a measurement distance of 300 mm from the source requires correction, which can be obtained from the characterisation measurement. As an example, the correction factors, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$, for a characterised source are given in Table 1. The correction factor is calculated relatively to a detector with an input optics diameter of $D = 12$ mm. The measurement uncertainty is estimated by the standard deviation calculated from 5 positions in the measurement plane: in the centre ($x = y = 0$ mm), 1 mm left/right and 1 mm up/down from the centre.

Detector diameter, D / mm	Homogeneity correction factor, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$	Standard uncertainty ($k = 1$)
10	0.998 17	0.000 08
15	1.003 48	0.000 11
20	1.011 45	0.000 20
25	1.022 55	0.000 21
30	1.037 24	0.000 18

Figure 6: Homogeneity at a distance of 300 mm. Correction factors for different input optics diameters of the detectors can be calculated from this characterisation.

Table 1: Example for correction factors, $f_{\text{hom,corr.}}$, to account for the non-ideal homogeneity at a measurement distance of 300 mm. As reference, a detector with an input optics diameter of $D = 12$ mm is taken.

Low spectral irradiance levels and limited spectral coverage

The main limitation of the newly developed source is the low irradiance level and the limited spectral coverage, mainly emitting radiation only in the IR-A spectral range. For comparison with a FEL 1000 transfer standard lamp, the ratio of the spectral irradiance is shown in Figure 7. As can be seen in the figure, the spectral irradiance of the newly developed source at 300 mm reaches only 0.08 % to 2.3 % of the FEL 1000 lamp measured at 700 mm between 710 nm and 1510 nm. Moreover, the developed source shows unwanted spectral features around 1185 nm and 1405 nm, most likely originating from absorption in the host material of the deposited long-wavelength phosphor.

Commercially available infrared phosphors, which would lead to higher irradiance levels, larger spectral coverage and a smoother spectrum, have not been found during project NEWSTAND.

Temporal drift

The measurement in Figure 8 shows the temporal stability of the source. Before the measurement, the LEDs have been seasoned for 1000 h, whereof 250 h together with the phosphors. While the LEDs quickly reach a stable output after switching on the source, the output of the phosphors tends to drift over an extended period of time. After a warm-up time of 48 h, the output of the short-wavelength phosphor (below 1150 nm) reaches 99.5 % of its nominal value with a drift of less than +0.007 %/h. The long-wavelength phosphor (above 1200 nm) tends to be less stable and only reaches 97 % of its nominal output with a drift of less than +0.05 %/h. After interrupting the source for 14 h, the phosphor's output falls back to a lower level and slowly starts to increase again. The origin of this behaviour is not understood yet.

Figure 7: Ratio of spectral irradiances between the newly developed source measured at 300 mm, $E_{e,\lambda}$, and a FEL 1000 transfer standard lamp at 700 mm, $E_{e,\lambda}$ (FEL 1000).

Figure 8: Temporal stability. The source has been off for 1 week before switch-on. After 124 h, the source was switched off 14 h and then switched on again. The integrated spectral irradiance values, $E_e(t)$, are normalised to the values attained after 475 h, $E_e(t = 475 \text{ h})$.

The issue of temporal drift, together with the low spectral irradiance levels and limited spectral coverage, prevents the source from serving as a reliable transfer standard for disseminating the spectral irradiance quantity.

4. Sources based on IR LEDs

4.1. Design description

Two prototype sources have been produced within the scope of the project. The *RISE-Fiber* and the *RISE-LED* sources were developed and used in the project intercomparison.

4.1.1. RISE-Fiber

The RISE-Fiber source is based on high-power LEDs from Thorlabs, each with a drive current between 800 mA and 1000 mA. The LEDs are mounted in heat-sunk encapsulation and prepared for coupling of the radiation into an optical fibre, providing a relatively stable operating condition, see Figure 9.

Figure 9: Commercially available fibre-coupled LED, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

In order to combine the radiation from several LEDs, a fibre bundle is used, also available from Thorlabs. The fibre bundle uses 7 individual fibres which are combined side-by-side at the output end, see Figure 10.

Figure 10: Commercially available fibre-bundle, used for the RISE-Fiber source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The fibres are connected using standard fibre-optic SMA connectors which simplifies the use. The output is also a fibre connector, see Figure 11. The radiation is directly available from the connector, or a patch cable could be used to bring the radiation to a more suitable position.

Figure 11: Fibre-bundle common output, showing the 7 fibre ends. Picture from Thorlabs.

4.1.2. RISE-LED

The RISE-LED source is based on standard infrared LED components which are commercially available. For RISE-LED, components with an incorporated lens were used. Each component was in either a TO-46 or TO-18 package, see Figure 12.

Figure 12: LED components used for RISE-LED source. Picture from Thorlabs.

The LED components were placed side-by-side using a standard circuit board. They were connected together according to their required drive current so that LEDs using the same drive current were connected in series, with a maximum of 5 LEDs in series. In total, 21 LEDs were used in the wavelength range from 780 nm to 1100 nm (centre wavelength).

In order to stabilise the temperature of RISE-LED, a thermally conducting epoxy was used to encapsulate the individual components, as seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Image of the lit source RISE-LED, showing the thermally conducting epoxy (grey).

A heater wire was also added to the epoxy which may be used to regulate the operating temperature to a temperature slightly above the temperature achieved when running the LEDs. A simple temperature controller with an on/off functionality and an embedded NTC resistor was used for this purpose.

4.2. Specifications

4.2.1. RISE-Fiber

The components used to assemble the source are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. RISE-Fiber source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
M780F2	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (780 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 28 nm (typ.) 800 mA maximum drive current 16 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1600 mW electrical power consumption
M810F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (810 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3600 mW electrical power consumption
M850F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (850 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3200 mW electrical power consumption
M880F2	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (880 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 7.8 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1700 mW electrical power consumption
M940F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (940 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 30 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 3800 mW electrical power consumption

Table 2. RISE-Fiber source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
M970F3	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (970 ± 10) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 16 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1900 mW electrical power consumption
M1100F1	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1100 ± 50) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 1000 mA maximum drive current 10 mW optical power (in 600 µm fibre) 1800 mW electrical power consumption
BF76LS01	Thorlabs	Fanout bundle, 7 fibres (FT600EMT) 600 µm core, low-OH fibre Numerical Aperture (NA): 0.39 (400 to 2200) nm SMA connectors 1 m total length
SLC-MA12-U	Mightex	12-channel LED Driver USB computer control 1 mA resolution 1000 mA maximum current

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 3.

Table 3. RISE-Fiber source drive settings.

LED	Drive current // I_{max} / %
M780F2	60
M810F3	50
M850F3	50
M880F2	100
M940F3	60
M970F3	100
M1100F1	80

The setting in Table 3 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Spectral irradiance, $E_{e,\lambda}$, of the RISE-Fiber source at 10 cm distance from connector end-face.

The figure shows the measured irradiance, however, it is limited by the spectrometer sensitivity near 1100 nm. Also, the centre wavelength of the 1100 nm LED is most likely between 1100 nm and 1150 nm.

The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured, but it is indicated by Figure 15.

Figure 15: Image of the RISE-Fiber source irradiance distribution at 10 cm distance from connector end-face.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 10 cm from the connector end-face. A usable area of at least 30 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle.

The entire RISE-Fiber source is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Image of the RISE-Fiber source. Inset shows the connector end-face.

4.2.2. RISE-LED

The components used to assemble the source are listed in Table 4.

Table 4. RISE-LED source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
LED780L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (780 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 25 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED800L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (800 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 30 mW optical power
LED810L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (810 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED830L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (830 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 32 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED840L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (840 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 35 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED870L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (870 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 25 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED890L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (890 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 44 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 18 mW optical power
LED910L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (910 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 44 nm (typ.)

Table 4. RISE-LED source components.

Item	Manufacturer/Supplier	Data
		75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
LED930L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (930 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 60 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 22 mW optical power
365-1579-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 935 nm Bandwidth 80 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 5 mW optical power
LED940E	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength 940 nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 6 mW optical power ∅ 5 mm epoxy casing
TSTS7100-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 950 nm Bandwidth 30 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 17 mW optical power
LED970L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (970 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 46 nm (typ.) 75 mA maximum drive current 33 mW optical power
EOLD-980-015-1	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (980 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 46 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 23 mW optical power
1125-1415-ND (2X)	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (1020 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 20 mW optical power 2 LEDs used
LED1050L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1050 ± 50) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 8 mW optical power
1125-1498-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength 1070 nm Bandwidth 74 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 24 mW optical power
LED1070L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1070 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 55 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 8 mW optical power
LED1085L	Thorlabs	Centre wavelength (1085 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 50 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 10 mW optical power
5242-EOLD- 1100-015-1-ND	DigiKey	Centre wavelength (1100 ± 20) nm Bandwidth 57 nm (typ.) 100 mA maximum drive current 24 mW optical power

The source is normally driven with the settings according to Table 5.

Table 5. RISE-LED source drive settings.

LED	Driver circuit no.	Drive current I / mA
LED780L	1	70
LED800L	2	50
LED810L	2	50
LED830L	2	50
LED840L	2	50
LED870L	1	70
LED890L	1	70
LED910L	3	75
LED930L	3	75
365-1579-ND	8	100
LED940E	4	70
TSTS7100-ND	5	20
LED970L	6	50
EOLD-980-015-1	6	50
1125-1415-ND	4	70
LED1050L	4	70
1125-1498-ND	4	70
LED1070L	7	60
LED1085L	7	60
EOLD-1100-015	7	60

The setting in Table 5 renders the spectral content shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Spectral irradiance, $E_{e,\lambda}$, of the RISE-LED source at 30 cm distance from the source circuit board surface.

Due to the much larger source size, it is necessary to use the source at 30 cm distance. The uniformity of the source has not been explicitly measured but it is indicated by Figure 18.

Figure 18: Image of the RISE-LED source irradiance distribution at 30 cm distance from source surface.

The picture shows the illumination on a millimetre-scale paper placed 30 cm from the source. A usable area of at least 40 mm in diameter is feasible, as indicated by the red circle.

The entire RISE-LED source is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Image of the RISE-LED source. Right picture is obtained with an infrared-sensitive camera.

4.3. Safety and handling instructions

The sources have been assessed according to the standard for photobiological safety of lamps and lamps systems, EN IEC 62471:2006. The sources RISE-Fiber and RISE-LED are found to belong to the Exempt group of lamps, see results in Annex A Photobiological safety.

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames.

Particular for RISE-Fiber

- The source is powered by the incorporated LED driver box, which in turn is controlled by a LabView program on a USB-connected computer. In the software, the current can be regulated between 0 % and 100 % of the maximum for each LED, meaning that it is safe to adjust anything from the software (LED-driver -4.vi).

Particular for RISE-LED

- The source is powered by the LED driver PCB. The currents are set using a trim-potentiometer on the PCB. Only 24 Vdc is required to be connected.
- The source has a temperature control PCB (+12 Vdc supply) which can be used to stabilise the temperature. Since only heating is possible, the set temperature must be higher than the temperature when the LEDs are lit, typically near +50 °C.
- Source is hot to the touch.

4.4. Operating conditions

Environment

Conditions with ambient temperature between 20 °C and 30 °C and relative humidity between 30 % and 70 % are recommended.

Thermal stability

For reproducibility, the sources shall be operated in stable laboratory conditions in terms of air flow and temperature.

Electrical parameters

The LEDs are driven by controlled LED drivers and should normally not require any adjustment.

Alignment and reference plane

The reference plane for RISE-Fiber is the end-face of the connector. For alignment purposes, distance and optical axis must be determined based on the connector symmetry. The recommended measurement distance is 100 mm.

The reference plane for RISE-LED is the circuit board surface. For alignment purposes, distance and optical axis must be determined based on the circuit board symmetry. The recommended measurement distance is 300 mm.

Spatial homogeneity

The irradiance spatial homogeneity has not been determined, but it is expected to handle entrance optics with diameters up to 30 mm to 40 mm at the measurement distance.

Spectral homogeneity

The spectral lateral homogeneity at the measurement distance has not been determined.

Temporal stability

A warm-up time of minimum 15 min should be allowed. Before the first use, the source should be seasoned for at least 100 h and the output monitored in regular intervals.

4.5. Limitations

The main limitations of the source in comparison with a standard QTH lamp are:

- Spectral variation of irradiance
- Irradiance spatial homogeneity
- Spectral lateral homogeneity
- Irradiance level is low

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Annex A Photobiological safety

The sources have been assessed according to the standard for photobiological safety of lamps and lamps systems, EN IEC 62471:2006. All sources are found to belong to the Exempt group of lamps.

The results for the source based on red LEDs and IR phosphors are presented in Table 6 and Table 7.

Table 6: Summary of the exposure limits for the surface of the skin or cornea (irradiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Limiting aperture (rad) / (deg)	Exposure limit in terms of constant irradiance for Exempt group ($W \cdot m^{-2}$)	Measurement value ($W \cdot m^{-2}$)
Actinic UV skin & eye	$E_S = \sum E_\lambda \cdot S(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	200 – 400	30000	1.4 / 80	0.001	N/A
Eye UV-A	$E_{UVA} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	315 – 400	1000	1.4 / 80	10	N/A
Blue-light small source	$E_B = \sum E_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 – 700	10000	< 0.011 / 0.63	1.0	N/A
Eye IR	$E_{IR} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 – 3000	1000	1.4 / 80	100	1.1
Skin thermal	$E_H = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 – 3000	10	2π sr	3557	2.0

Table 7: Summary of the exposure limits for the retina (radiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Field of view (rad)	Exposure limit in terms of constant radiance for Exempt group ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot sr^{-1}$)	Measurement value ($W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot sr^{-1}$)
Blue light	$L_B = \sum L_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 – 700	10000	0.1	100	0.45
Retinal thermal	$L_R = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 – 1400	10	0.011	$1.12 \cdot 10^6$ ($\alpha = 0.025$ rad)	$9.2 \cdot 10^2$
Retinal thermal (weak visual stimulus)	$L_{IR} = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 – 1400	1000	0.011	$2.4 \cdot 10^5$ ($\alpha = 0.025$ rad)	N/A

The assessment of the sources RISE-Fiber and RISE-LED is based on measurement of radiation at 200 mm distance from the source and subsequent calculation of irradiance/radiance and comparison with exposure limits, see results in Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Summary of the exposure limits for the surface of the skin or cornea (irradiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Limiting aperture (rad) / (deg)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ²)	Measurement value (W/m ²)
Actinic UV skin & eye	$E_S = \sum E_\lambda \cdot S_{UV}(\lambda)$	200 - 400	30000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Eye UV-A	$E_{UVA} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	315 - 400	1000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Blue-light small source	$E_B = \sum E_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	< 0.011	N/A	N/A
Eye IR	$E_{IR} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 3000	1000	1,4 / 80	101.2	2.5
Skin thermal	$E_H = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 3000	10	2π sr	3557	3

Summary of the exposure limits for the retina (radiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Field of view (rad)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ² /sr)	Measurement value (W/m ² /sr)
Blue light	$L_B = \sum L_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	0.1000	N/A	N/A
Retinal thermal	$L_R = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 1400	10	0.0110	2.56E+06	1.46E+04
Retinal thermal (weak visual stimulus)	$L_{IR} = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 1400	1000	0.011	5.45E+05	1.18E+04

Figure 20: Results for RISE-Fiber lamp, assessed at 200 mm distance according to requirements for Exempt Group in EN IEC 62471.

Summary of the exposure limits for the surface of the skin or cornea (irradiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Limiting aperture (rad) / (deg)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ²)	Measurement value (W/m ²)
Actinic UV skin & eye	$E_S = \sum E_\lambda \cdot S_{UV}(\lambda)$	200 - 400	30000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Eye UV-A	$E_{UVA} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	315 - 400	1000	1,4 / 80	N/A	N/A
Blue-light small source	$E_B = \sum E_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	< 0.011	N/A	N/A
Eye IR	$E_{IR} = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 3000	1000	1,4 / 80	101.2	25.2
Skin thermal	$E_H = \sum E_\lambda \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 3000	10	2π sr	3557	26

Summary of the exposure limits for the retina (radiance based values)

Hazard name	Relevant equation	Wavelength range (nm)	Exposure duration (s)	Field of view (rad)	Exposure limit Exempt group (W/m ² /sr)	Measurement value (W/m ² /sr)
Blue light	$L_B = \sum L_\lambda \cdot B(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	300 - 700	10000	0.1000	N/A	N/A
Retinal thermal	$L_R = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	380 - 1400	10	0.0110	2.81E+05	1.89E+04
Retinal thermal (weak visual stimulus)	$L_{IR} = \sum L_\lambda \cdot R(\lambda) \cdot \Delta\lambda$	780 - 1400	1000	0.011	6.00E+04	1.77E+04

Figure 21: Results for RISE-LED lamp, assessed at 200 mm distance according to requirements for Exempt Group in EN IEC 62471.